

EVALUATION OF THE TREATMENT QUALITY FOR PATIENTS WITH ORAL MUCOSAL LESIONS

Abdullaev Davlat Mukumovich

Samarkand State Medical University Department of Skin and
Venereal

Kamolova Moxinur Iskandarovna

Samarkand State Medical University Department

Abdullaev Xasan Davlatovich

Samarkand regional branch of the Republican Specialized
Dermatovenerological and Cosmetology Scientific and
Practical Medical Center/ Samarkand State Medical
University

Annotation: this article attempts to reveal the main reasons for the development of a staged treatment of patients with lesions of the oral mucosa with lichen planus, recommendations for the treatment of this pathology for dermatovenerologists and dentists. To carry out scientific work, the author involved 527 patients with lichen planus with localizations of rashes in the oral cavity. Conducted a clinical, laboratory and psychological study of patients in the process of treatment in the dermatovenerological department of the regional clinical hospital. The problem in question is still little studied, and therefore requires more thorough research.

Key words: Lichen planus, oral cavity, treatment.

Introduction: Lichen planus is an inflammatory dermatosis with diverse clinical manifestations, involving the skin, its appendages (hair, nails) and mucous membranes. It is characterized by polymorphism of rashes, among which papules accompanied by itching are typical elements. The prevalence of lichen planus in Russia among adults aged 18 years and older in 2012 was 11.3 per 100,000 people. Most often, lichen planus occurs in people aged 30 to 60 years. In 5% of cases, the disease occurs in children. In the development of the disease, the main factor is an autoimmune reaction to the action of an unidentified epidermal neoantigen by basal layer keratinocytes, which results in the activation and migration of T-lymphocytes into the skin. T-lymphocytes produce substances that can destroy

basement membranes and cause apoptosis of basal keratinocytes.

Aim: development of a staged treatment of patients with lesions of the oral mucosa with lichen planus, recommendations for the treatment of this pathology for dermatovenereologists and dentists.

Materials and methods: 527 patients with lichen planus with lesions in the oral cavity were involved in the study. Conducted a clinical, laboratory and psychological study of patients in the process of treatment in the dermatovenerological department of the regional clinical hospital.

Results: patients with lichen planus were treated with the help of drug therapy (vitamin therapy, regenerating therapy, transcranial electrical stimulation, hirudotherapy, acupuncture, local healing therapy). In severe cases of the erosive-ulcerative form of the disease, corticosteroids were prescribed orally according to the scheme with further withdrawal of the drug. The clinical picture of the disease, the dynamics of laboratory parameters (hemogram, biochemical data, cultural examination of the oral mucosa, psychological examination using MMPI, the Zung depression scale, the defensiveness scale) were monitored. The treatment algorithm was defined. The first stage is the sanitation of the oral cavity and tonsils by a dentist and an otolaryngologist on an outpatient basis. The second stage is inpatient treatment of patients in the dermatovenerology department with mandatory ultrasound examination of internal organs, endoscopic examination, examination of feces for intestinal dysbiosis, and treatment of concomitant diseases. The third stage is outpatient dental supervision, prosthetics, spa treatment of gastrointestinal pathology.

Conclusions: the observation of a large number of patients with lichen planus with lesions of the oral cavity showed the effectiveness of staged treatment, including drug therapy, physiotherapy, reflexology.

Literature:

1. Davlatovich A. X. VAGINAL TRIXOMONADLAR SHTAMMASINI TRIXOPOLGA VA XIMOTRIPSIN BILAN BILAN SEZGICHLIGINI

ANIQLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 645-647.

2. Davlatovich A. X., Orifovich S. D., Baxtiyorovich A. S. Studying the Relationship of Local Immune Status and the Course of Burn Disease //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 679-682.
3. Xolmurodovich D. J., Umidovich N. T., Davlatovich A. X. CLINIC COURSE OF NONSPECIFIC PNEUMONIA //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 510-513.
4. Абдуллаев Х. Д. и др. ЛАЗЕР В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ВИТИЛИГО //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 495-500.
5. Hikmatovich I. N. et al. The use of Fungite in the Local Treatment of Genital Herpes //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 231-232.
6. Davlatovich A. X., O'gli A. B. X., O'gli I. A. S. BOLALARDA GENITAL GERPESNI DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 367-369.
7. Xolmurodovich D. J., Orifovich R. S., Davlatovich A. X. FEATURES OF THE MICROELEMENT STATUS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN CHILDREN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 447-450.
8. Davlatovich A. X. DETERMINATION OF GENE ACTIVITY IN VITILIGO PATIENTS //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 451-454.
9. Davlatovich A. X. et al. EVALUATION OF THE GENERAL SOMATIC STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH VITILIGO BASED ON THE DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF NATURAL ANTIBODIES TO VARIOUS ORGANIS AND TISSUES OF THE BODY //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 472-476.

10. Davlatovich A. X. et al. USING IMMUNOMAX AND 0.1% TACROLIMUS OINTMENT IN THE TREATMENT OF VITILIGO //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 559-562.
11. Абдуллаев Х., Толибов М. Allergodermatozlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan vulgar acneni kompleks davolash Samaraligini o'rganish //Журнал гепатогастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.2. – С. 73-74.
12. Ахмедов Ш. К. и др. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ИЗОТРЕТИНОИНА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ УГРЕВОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ //Академический журнал Западной Сибири. – 2015. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 56-56.
13. Нуруллаева А. А., Рахматова А. Х., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МИКРОБНОГО ОБСЕМЕНЕНИЯ КОЖИ ПРИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ЗУДЯЩИХ ДЕРМАТОЗАХ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2019. – С. 125-125.
14. Абдуллаев Х. Д., Собиров М. С., Жумаева Д. Х. НЕРВНО-ПСИХИЧЕСКИЙ СТАТУС У БОЛЬНЫХ СЕБОРЕЕЙ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2018. – С. 115-116.
15. Iskandarovna K. M. SIFILISNING IMMUNOASSAY SHAKLLARI //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 534-536.
16. Iskandarovna K. M., Dilshodovna A. D., Adxamovna A. A. Impact of Socio-Hygienic Conditions of Life on the Health of Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 644-646.
17. Iskandarovna K. M. et al. Comprehensive Assessment of the Levels of Somatic Health and Disturbances of Adaptation Reserves in Medical Students //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 641-643.
18. Iskandarovna K. M., Alamovich K. A., Rabbimovich N. A. Treatment of Urethrogenic Prostatitis Associated with Chlamydia Infection //ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 44-46.

19. Iskandarovna K. M., Buribaevna I. S., Azamovna A. N. Immunoassay Forms of Syphilis //TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – С. 47-49.
20. Ахмедова М. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОНИХОМИКОЗОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-190.
21. Абдуллаев Д. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КРЕМАТЕРБИЗИЛ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ МИКОЗОВ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 181-185.